

The newsletter of the BIOSKEL lab

02

Collaborations

02

Projects

04

Industry

04

In the media

04

Science in brief

05

Training

06

Publications

03 Focus on
bone regeneration

Collaborations

New academic collaborations...

Nathalie Busso (Department of Musculoskeletal Medicine, University of Lausanne, Switzerland)

Marthe Rousseau (SAINBIOSE-UMR INSERM 1059, Saint-Étienne, France)

William Fenical (Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California San Diego, USA)

Iván Valdebenito (School of Aquaculture, Catholic University of Temuco, Chile)

Kai Kristoffer Lie and Kristin Hamre (Institute of Marine Research, Bergen, Norway)

Rui Gonçalves (BIOMIN GmbH, Getzersdorf, Austria)

Carlos Andrade and Natasha Nogueira (Centro de Maricultura da Calheta, Madeira, Portugal)

Paulo Caldeira and Graça Sequeira (Centro Hospitalar Universitário do Algarve, Faro, Portugal)

... and industry contracts

Biomin GmbH (Austria)

Algenuity (United Kingdom)

SPAROS Lda. (Portugal)

Projects

Mar2020

BIOSKEL lab was awarded two MAR2020 projects to improve farmed fish quality using novel marine ingredients.

Project **ALGASOLE** will evaluate the ability of extracts prepared from macroalgae rich in vitamin K to improve skeletal status reproduction capacity and immune response of the Senegalese sole.

Project **OSTEOMAR** aims at discovering new marine derived bioactive extracts for applications in marine fish nutrition, in order to improve growth and reduce skeletal deformities.

Interreg

The ES-PT collaborative project ALGARED+ aims at developing inovative products with micro-algae and the BIOSKEL lab will assess osteogenic bioactivities.
Web: www.algared.com

Atlantic Area

BIOSKEL lab is participating in the project "Blue biotechnology as a road for innovation on human's health aiming smart growth in Atlantic Area."
Web: bluehuman.cetmar.org

European projects

As part of the CCMAR, BIOSKEL lab is involved in the EU infra-structures **ASSEMBLE plus** and **EMBRC** through Joint Research Activities (JRA) and transnational access (TA).

COST

M. Leonor Cancela represents Portugal in the European network for connective tissue calcifying diseases (**EuroSoft- CalcNet** COST action 16115)
Web: www.cost.eu

Bone regenerative medicine: Insights from caudal fin regeneration in zebrafish

The ability of zebrafish to fully regenerate its caudal fin was explored within the scope of João Cardeira's PhD thesis to better understand the mechanisms underlying *de novo* bone formation

While mammals, in particular humans, have a limited ability to regenerate tissues, other vertebrates, like teleost fish, can fully restore lost or damaged body parts such as heart, retina, kidney, spinal cord, brain and fins. Understanding how vertebrates regenerate lost tissues and identifying the underlying mechanisms is crucial not only from a basic scientific point of view but also towards the development of novel therapies for a variety of degenerative and traumatic diseases. More specifically, unveiling the complex mechanisms leading to *de novo* bone formation and mineralization is of great importance for skeletal regenerative medicine. The caudal fin of the zebrafish is a valuable model system for regenerative biology as fin tissues are organized in a simple architecture and their restoration can be easily monitored in detail over time. Caudal fin regeneration is also remarkably fast (< 2 weeks).

The first part of this work was published in *Scientific Reports* in 2016 and provides a detailed description of the regenerative and mineralogenic profiles but also of the main events occurring during fin regeneration and lepidotrichia mineralization. This data was used to develop a methodology to rapidly and accurately assess the regenerative and mineralogenic performances of selected compounds through histomorphometric parameters. Proof-of-concept experiments successfully demonstrated the suitability of this system to study the mechanisms underlying bone formation and patterning.

The transcriptome of regenerates at stages of blastema formation (BF) and regenerative outgrowth (RO) were determined through RNA-Seq. Analysis of marker genes indicated that osteoclasts may be actively recruited during RO. The most up-regulated gene was the osteoclast regulator calcitonin (*calca*), suggesting that calcaregulated osteoclasts may play a central role in the formation of new bone and/or the patterning of the new rays. Ray patterning during fin regeneration in zebrafish may represent a good system to better understand mechanisms underlying digit malformations in human.

Assessment of regenerated and mineralized areas (*left*) and representation of fin regenerate fragments showing expected mineralogenic outcomes (*right*)

In the media

Transformer la recherche marine en biotechnologie

(27/09/2017)

Interview of M. Leonor Cancela following her presentation at the meeting *Les Rendez-vous de Concarneau* (France), where she presented recent data of BIOSKEL lab on the suitability of the zebrafish to model and study human skeletal disorders but also its use as a first-line screening system to discover novel marine compounds with bone anabolic properties and therapeutic potential.

Os peixes podem ajudar a combater a osteoporose?

Suinformação

(06/04/2017)

Interview of João Cardeira following the publication of his paper in *Scientific Reports* (Nature Publishing Group) on the ability of the zebrafish to regenerate his caudal fin – including the bony rays – and its suitability to investigate mechanisms underlying new bone formation. This knowledge could be decisive in the development of new therapies aiming at treating skeletal disorders such as osteoporosis.

Onde está o Danio? – nos bastidores do Zebrafish

informativo digital
NOTÍCIAS DO NORDESTE

(11/08/2017)

Interview of Lara Carvalho (Institute of Molecular Medicine) about zebrafish facilities in Portugal, recognizing the pioneer activity of the BIOSKEL laboratory – in particular M. Leonor Cancela – in the use of this model animal in studies aiming at deciphering the complex mechanisms of skeleton development and at establishing it as a suitable model of human bone disorders.

Science in brief

Osteotoxicity

The definition of osteotoxicity is “*damage to the bone by drugs, chemicals or any other compounds resulting in impaired bone formation, mineralization and remodeling*”. Within the scope of **AQUATOX** project financed by the FCT, BIOSKEL lab assessed the toxic effect of cadmium and 3-methylcholantrene and found that both are osteotoxicants, affecting the growth of the opercular bone and increasing the occurrence of skeletal deformities in zebrafish larvae and impairing the regeneration or the patterning of the fin rays. Stay alert, 3 papers will be published soon on this!

PDB

Paget’s disease of bone (PDB) is a metabolic bone disorder characterized by focal increases in bone remodelling, marked by excessive osteoclastic bone resorption and increased bone formation. The BIOSKEL lab investigates the genetic association of polymorphisms

with the pathogenesis of PDB in the Portuguese population in Algarve and Alentejo. This work is done in collaboration with the Centro Hospitalar Universitário do Algarve (CHUA).

Science in brief

Microplastics

“How microplastics and adsorbed pollutants affect zebrafish development” will be studied by Marco Tarasco within the scope of his PhD thesis (see below). The osteotoxicity of benzo[a]pyrene (BaP), a polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon ubiquitous in the aquatic environment, was assessed using several *in vivo* zebrafish systems and first results have confirmed the toxic effect of BaP on bone formation and mineralization. A plastic-free housing system was specifically designed to expose zebrafish to microplastics and assess their effect.

Farmed fish nutrition

BIOSKEL lab is testing new feed ingredients to improve farmed fish quality, with a particular focus on skeletogenesis and the reduction of deformities in fish skeleton. The requirement for vitamins A and K and effects of phospholipids (PC and PE) and minerals (Zn and Sr) have been determined in zebrafish and sole and new diet formulations are being evaluated (projects ZEBRAFEEDS and LARVAMIX). PC is beneficial for reproduction, Zn (60 mg/kg) and vitamin K (250 mg/kg) are beneficial for skeletal development.

Training

Students hosted in the lab...

Marco Tarasco (Italy), a new PhD student of BIOSKEL lab financed by the FCT

FCT
Fundação
para a Ciência
e a Tecnologia

Yulia Chaumel (Spain; ERASMUS), **Matthew Carson** (United Kingdom) and **Ana Manuela de Azevedo** (Spain)

- MSc in Molecular Biology & Microbiology: **Tatiana Varela, Debora Varela, Tatiana Authier, Sara Mariano**
- MSc in Medicine: **Kevin Azevedo, Teresa Castro, Nuno Carrasco**
- BSc in Biomedical Sciences: **Domingos Prata, Nicole Gilotay, Xavier Anastácio, Cristina Marcut, Ana Rita Pinho, Catarina Frederico**

... and that defended their PhD

- April 10: **João Cardeira** (UALG, ProRegeM PhD programme)
- May 24: **Márcio Simão** (UALG, DCBM)

Publications

- Boglione C, Gavaia P, Koumoundouros G, Gisbert E, Moren M, Fontagné S, Witten PE** (2017) Skeletal anomalies in reared European fish larvae and juveniles. Part 1: Normal and anomalous skeletogenic processes. In: Conceição LEC, and Tandler A [Eds] *Success factors for fish larval production*. John Wiley & Sons, Oxford, UK. pp. 219-254 - [ISBN: 978-1-119-07216-4](#)
- Boglione C, Gisbert E, Gavaia P, Witten PE, Moren M, Fontagné S, Koumoundouros G** (2017) Skeletal anomalies in reared European fish larvae and juveniles. Part 2: Main typologies, occurrences and causative factors. In: Conceição LEC, and Tandler A [Eds] *Success factors for fish larval production*. John Wiley & Sons, Oxford, UK. pp. 255-330 - [ISBN: 978-1-119-07216-4](#)
- Carvalho FR, Fernandes AR, Cancela ML, Gavaia PJ** (2017) Improved regeneration and *de novo* bone formation in a diabetic zebrafish model treated with Paricalcitol and Cinacalcet. *Wound Repair and Regeneration* 25:432-442 - [DOI: 10.1111/wrr.12536](#)
- Fernández I, Ortiz-Delgado JB, Darias MJ, Hontoria F, Andree KB, Manchado M, Sarasquete C, Gisbert E** (2017) Vitamin A affects flatfish development in a thyroid hormone signaling and metamorphic stage dependent manner. *Frontiers in Physiology* 8:458 - [DOI: 10.3389/fphys.2017.00458](#)
- Ferreira-Rodriguez N, Fernández I, Varandas S, Cortes R, Cancela ML, Pardo I** (2017) The role of calcium concentration on *Corbicula fluminea* invasiveness capacity in crystalline basins. *Science of the Total Environment* 580:1363-1370 - [DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.12.100](#)
- Koumoundouros G, Gisbert E, Fernández I, Cabrita E, Galindo-Villegas J, Conceição L** (2017) Quality descriptors and predictors in farmed marine fish larvae and juveniles. In: Conceição LEC, and Tandler A [Eds] *Success factors for fish larval production*. John Wiley & Sons, Oxford, UK. pp. 443-463 - [ISBN: 978-1-119-07216-4](#)
- Marques C, Roberto V, Granadeiro L, Trindade M, Gavaia PJ, Laizé V, Cancela ML, Fernández I** (2017) The xenobiotic sensor PXR in a marine flatfish species (*Solea senegalensis*): gene expression patterns and its regulation under different physiological conditions. *Marine Environmental Research* 130:187-199 - [DOI: 10.1016/j.marenvres.2017.07.021](#)
- Riesco MF, Oliveira C, Soares F, Gavaia PJ, Dinis MT, Cabrita E** (2017) *Solea senegalensis* sperm cryopreservation: New insights on sperm quality. *PLoS ONE* 12: e0186542 - [DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0186542](#)
- Surget G, Roberto V, Le Lann K, Mira S, Guérard F, Laizé V, Poupart N, Cancela ML, Stiger-Pouvreau V** (2017) Marine green macroalgae: a source of natural compounds with mineralogenic and antioxidant activities. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 29:575-584 - [DOI: 10.1007/s10811-016-0968-3](#)
- Tarasco M, Laizé V, Cardeira J, Cancela ML, Gavaia PJ** (2017) The zebrafish operculum: a powerful system to assess osteogenic bioactivities of molecules with pharmacological and toxicological relevance. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part C: Toxicology & Pharmacology* 197:45-52 - [DOI: 10.1016/j.cbpc.2017.04.006](#)

Interdisciplinary Approaches
In Fish Skeletal Biology

5th Meeting
16-19 April 2018
Tavira, Portugal

<http://iafsb.org/>